

The Influence of Consumer Attitude on Behavioral Intention in the Choice of Gasoline Station

Suzy Mae D. Redillas¹, Jerald D. Sevilla², Charmaine F. Papna³,
Jovenil R. Bacatan⁴

^{1,2,3,4}UM Peñaplata College, Island Garden City of Samal, Philippines
Corresponding Author: jovenilbacatan@umindanao.edu.ph

Date of Submission: 14-10-2023

Date of Acceptance: 31-10-2023

ABSTRACT: The main purpose of this study was to determine the significant relationship between the Consumer Attitude and Behavioral Intention of the customers in choosing gasoline stations in Samal District. The study utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. The data was gathered through the use of survey questionnaires and was distributed personally and randomly to 385 customers of gasoline stations in Samal District. The result showed that the consumer attitude generated a high mean score and shows that the items were oftentimes manifested while behavioral intention also had a high mean score and shows that the items were oftentimes manifested. Moreover, there was a significant relationship between consumer attitude and behavioral intention. It was also found out that consumer attitude significantly influence behavioral intention in the choice of gasoline station. The researchers recommended that a gasoline station should improve their marketing strategy, like giving a discount or promo to their product, improve the quality of service and accommodation because customers oftentimes choose a specific gasoline station according to their attitude and behavioral intention.

KEYWORDS: consumer attitude, behavioral intention, gasoline stations, descriptive-correlation research design

I. INTRODUCTION

The consumers are ordinary people who engaged on activities related to purchase some products and services (Ajzen, 2008). They are the important assets of a business that should be

managed and valued (Gupta & Lehmann, 2003). Also, they are the one of the factors where a business runs and prosper. The attitude of a consumer is either they are favorable or unfavorable towards a person, place, an object or something. It is also the evaluation of some aspects in the mind of consumers that results to a positive or negative decision making (Pande & Soodan, 2015). The behavior of a consumer and their intention can influence the possible action or behavior towards a business. If the intention is high, the behavior of a consumer is more likely to take place (Blomqvist et al. 2015). So, it is important to know the attitude and the behavior of a consumer because it tells how they are into the products and service of a business (Ajzen, 2008).

Nowadays, consumer choice of gasoline station has been an interest for many years (Kakunu, 2012). There are many choices for consumers to achieve satisfaction towards a product or service. Similar businesses compete just to acquire advantages in offering benefits from their products and services to their consumers. Gasoline stations needs to analyze the consumer attitude and behavior to apply marketing strategies on their target market (Tun, 2020).

In Kenya, fuels are the main source of their commercial energy. The retail service stations have been experiencing challenges like increasing of fuel price and newly emerge competitors in which the consumers can immediately switch from one gasoline station to another according to their attitude and behavior (Mwenda & Oloko, 2017). In Myanmar, the demand for gasoline station has increased in the past years. The numbers of gasoline station are increasing and become more competitive in which they want to get new customers and retain them (Tun, 2020).

In the Philippines, the oil industry faces a challenging situation especially for the retailers of gasoline prices and competition where competitors grow stronger and more numerous day by day (Jardeleza, 2004). Moreover, it is important to know the consumer's intention towards a gasoline station to have a positive possibility to stay on top in every situation.

The demand of fuel or gasoline has increased due to a high number of vehicles in Samal District. Lot of customers comes to refuel their vehicles to a specific gasoline station where we want to know how their attitude and intention makes them decide to choose a specific gasoline station. Conducting this study is very important especially for the gasoline stations in Samal District because through this research, it will help us know if the consumer's attitude is whether good or bad as well as their intention in choosing a gasoline station. Also, this study will determine the level of consumer attitude and behavioral intention in the choice of gasoline station in Samal District. Therefore, the result of this study will serve as a guide for the gasoline stations in Samal District and will provide ideas that will help them improve their product and service towards their consumers which may have a positive attitude and good intention in choosing a gasoline station.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Consumer Attitude

Consumer's attitude towards a product or service is shaped by their thoughts (cognition) and feelings (affect) about it (Schaufele & Janssen, 2021). Attitude is a permanent organization of motivational, emotional, perceptual, and cognitive processes. Khan (2019) also stated that an attitude is a collection of sentiments, convictions, and behaviors directed at a certain object. It also made up of three parts: affect, behavior, and cognition. Affect describes an object's emotional response; behavior describes a person's actions; and cognition describes the customer's mental process. These three factors influence a person's decision to engage in specific behavior. It also indicates environmental cues, such as the items offered to consumers and how they are presented, influence attitudes (Mothersbaugh et al. 2020).

In the study of Bhatt (2014), consumer attitude can be both a hindrance and a benefit to a marketer. In marketing terms, an attitude is described as a long-term evaluation of a product or service. An attitude meets a personal objective while

the gasoline. The gasoline business faces fluctuation

also influencing consumer spending and buying patterns. It also has a substantial impact on behavioral responses to marketing operations (Choppin & Darrat, 2000). Marketers build methods to influence consumer's decisions and achieve a competitive advantage in the market place by understanding their features and decision process (Kakunu, 2012).

In the study of Tun (2020), it presented a questionnaire of consumer attitude which composed of four (4) statements in order the consumers will answer or response. It stated there if a consumer has a positive buying attitude at a specific gasoline station; if they have a favorable attitude; if it is good to buy fuel at a specific gasoline station; and if they feel confident when they buy fuel at a specific gasoline station. Also, in the findings of its study the customers have positive buying attitude on the specific petrol station. They consider their attitude in which they are willing to try and they are planned to do, in order to choose a specific petrol station.

Behavioral Intention

Consumer's behavioral intention has been increasingly focused on product features and costs that can provide what the consumer desires. The methodical approach of consumers use while entering the purchase process and making purchasing decisions is characterized as behavior. When establishing marketing strategies, the step-by-step consumer decision making processes, as well as common decision-making modes, are both useful. Purchasing intent is an essential determinant of actual purchase behavior in the real world. When it comes to purchasing decisions, customers place a greater emphasis on emotional value, such as proximity to things and participation with them (Tun, 2019).

A notable and important predictor of the desire to utilize autonomous electric car services (AECS) is the behavioral intention to use electric car services (ECS). The behavioral intention to use ECS has a positive impact on the intention to use AECS, indicating that ECS users are often open to adopting ECS when outfitted with autonomous cars (Curtale, Liao & Rebalski, 2022). In the study of Khan (2019), the results show that the level or measure of consumer behavioral intention is high on purchasing Omera LPG. It means that assessing consumer behavioral intention towards purchasing Omera LPG is a useful one.

Moreover, in the study of Tun (2020), it presented a questionnaire of behavioral intention which composed of six (6) statements in order the consumers will answer or response. It stated there about their willingness to choose a specific gasoline station; if they intend to choose a specific gasoline station; if they intend to choose; if they consider, expect, want and try to choose a specific gasoline station if they possibly go to refuel. And according to its findings the general result for behavioral intention is high was it represents that the respondents accept that they positively have behavioral intention in the choice of petrol stat

Correlation between Consumer Attitude and Behavioral Intention

In the study of Khan (2019), it concludes that the more positive consumer attitude towards a brand will have a greater influence in their behavioral intention. Because a consumer's intention towards a brand matters, their behavioral intention is an important factor in their purchasing choice. If a consumer has a positive perception of a product, they are more likely to buy it.

Consumers with strong positive attitudes and behavioral intentions have the highest level of certainty which is also most durable whereas those with lesser attitudes and intents have much lower certainty levels (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006). Sandhe (2019) stated that there is a positive relationship among consumer attitude and purchasing intention. The general attitude was assessed to be moderately positive. The same was discovered in terms of purchasing intent; it was also assessed to be moderately positive.

Positive attitudes will influences behavioral intention towards using mobile services. With regards to using mobile services, attitude showed a substantial correlation with behavior and intention. As a result, when the relationship between attitudes and behavioral attention has been explored, it has become clear how important attitudes are determining behavior. When the coefficients of the attitude are evaluated, the presumption that attitudes have a significant, direct impact on intentions to use mobile services (Suki & Suki, 2011). The findings show in the study of Akter & Islam (2020) shows that the consumer attitudes towards green products have a positive influence on purchase intent. There is also a positive relationship between attitude and behavioral intention in purchases.

It was stated in the study of Khan (2019) that their model successfully describes customer behavioral intention when it comes to purchasing

liquefied petroleum gas (LPG). Omera LPG, as a brand, should pay special attention to one of the most important factors: attitude towards behavior. It only works if consumer behavior is considered as a relevant variable and acted upon. And because its beta value is very highly correlated with it, then it is clear that attitude towards behavior was the most crucial to customer satisfaction.

Moreover, it is also found in the study of Ho (2013) that the outcomes and conclusions demonstrated that consumer expressed a willingness to make future online purchases, and that attitude is positively and significantly connected with behavioral intention. The study came to the conclusion that attitudes are directly influenced by the perceived advantages of buying, trustworthiness of the merchant, customer lifestyle, and consumer prior experience. On the contrary, Rashid and Khan (2017) stated in their study that the analysis of the results revealed that the customer attitude is not a good predictor of consumer behavior because there may be other mediating factors that affect the final purchase intention and behavior of consumers.

Lastly, according to the study of Tun (2020), consumers' attitude is significant on behavioral intention in the choice of petrol station. An attitude has a beneficial impact on the behavioral intention when choosing a gas station. They have an impact on their behavior, which they are willing to try and plan to exert in order to choose a specific gas station. In addition, they will aim to purchase gasoline from a specific gasoline station, and they will then attempt to purchase gasoline from that station.

III. METHOD

Research Design

This study used a quantitative descriptive correlation research design to determine the influence of consumer attitude on the behavioral intention in the choice of gasoline station. According to Boru (2018), a research design is procedures to collect, analyze, interpret and report a data in such research studies. A descriptive correlation research design describes the variables and its relationship that naturally occur between and among them (Sousal et al. 2007). It helps the researchers to acquire certain information in conducting this study.

Research Locale and Respondents

This study was conducted on the gasoline stations located in Samal District. The researchers choose this place to gather information to the customers about their attitude and behavioral

intention in choosing a gasoline station. The respondents of this study were the customers of the gasoline stations in Samal District. By using Cochran's formula ($n = \frac{z^2}{4e^2}$) for unknown population, we will find its sample size in solving this: $n = \frac{(1.96)^2}{4(0.05)^2} = 384.16$. So, the researchers randomly select a 385 sample size of respondents who are the customers of the gasoline stations in Samal District.

Research Instrument

The source of data was gathered through a survey questionnaire. The researchers were using an adapted questionnaire from the study of Khaing Tazin Tun for the consumer attitude and behavioral intention. The instrument consists of about 4 questions with a 5-point Likert scale for the responses of consumer attitude. For behavioral intention, it consists of 6 questions with a 5-point Likert scale for responses.

Data Analyses

The data was analyzed using SPSS version 22. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to treat the data. The mean was used to measure the level the consumer attitude and behavioral intention in the choice of gasoline station. In addition, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the significance of the relationship between consumer attitude and behavioral intention. Lastly, the Simple Linear Regression was used to determine the significant influence of consumer attitude on the behavioral intention in the choice of gasoline station.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Consumer Attitude

Table 1 reflects the data on the level of consumer attitude of the customer of the gasoline stations in Samal District. The table reveals the total mean score which is 4.08 with a standard deviation of .82. The mean score is described as *high level* and shows that items in the consumer attitude are oftentimes manifested. The result was the same in the study of Ndlazi et al. (2021); it reveals that it was more likely to have a favorable attitude toward a gas station. Also, the most influential component in the result of the study of Tun (2019) was the attitude of the customers and increasing in attitude component will have a positive impact in general. Also, in the study of Tun (2020), the customers have positive buying attitude on the specific gas station. They consider their attitude in which they are

willing to try and they are planned to do, in order to choose a specific gas station.

Table 1: Level of Consumer Attitude

Variable	SD	M	Descriptive Level
Overall Consumer Attitude Level	.82	4.08	High

Note: N = 385, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Level Behavioral Intention

Table 2 reflects the data on the level of behavioral intention of the customer of the gasoline stations in Samal District. The table reveals the total mean score which is 4.13 with a standard deviation of .90. The mean score is described as *high level* and shows that items in the behavioral intention are oftentimes manifested. The result was also in line with the study of Tun (2020), it appears that the general result for behavioral intention is high were it represents that the respondents accept that they positively have behavioral intention in the choice of gas station. In the study of Khan (2019), the results show that the level or measure of consumer behavioral intention is high. It means that assessing consumer behavioral intention is an important one.

Table 2: Level of Behavioral Intention

Variable	SD	M	Descriptive Level
Overall Behavioral Intention Level	.90	4.13	High

Note: N = 385, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Significance of the Relationship between Consumer Attitude and Behavioral Intention

The test of correlation of Consumer attitude and Behavioral intention is reflected in Table 3. The data reveal the overall computed r-value of .826 which means that their degree of correlation was strong which is said to be a significant correlation. The p-value of this was less than 0.05. The confidence level set for this study was $p < 0.000$ therefore, the result rejected the hypothesis of no significant relationship between Consumer attitude and Behavioral intention.

Table 3: Significance of the Relationship between Consumer Attitude and Behavioral Intention

Consumer Attitude	Behavioral Intention
	Overall
Overall	.826* (.000)

$p < .05$

The findings are consistent in the study of Tun (2020), consumers attitude is significant on behavioral intention in the choice of gas station. An attitude has a beneficial impact on the behavioral intention when choosing a gas station. They have an impact on their behavior, which they are willing to try and plan to exert in order to choose a specific gas station. Also, it is also found in the study of Ho (2013) that attitude is positively and significantly connected with behavioral intention. Furthermore, Suki and Suki (2011) stated that the attitude showed a substantial correlation with behavior and intention and when the relationship between attitudes and behavioral attention has been explored, it has become clear how important attitudes are determining behavior. When the coefficients of the attitude are evaluated, the presumption is that attitudes have a significant, direct impact on intentions.

Significance of the Influence of Consumer Attitude to the Behavioral Intention

Presented in Table 4 is the regression analysis that revealed the influence of consumer attitude on the behavioral intention in the choice of gasoline station. The obtained F-value of 821.423 is significant at $p < 0.05$ which indicated a model fit. Also, the R-squared value of .682 suggested that F the variance in member satisfaction was attributed to the indicators of service quality specified in this study. This means that .318 or 31.8% of the variance could be credited to other things that are already beyond the concern of this study.

The consumer attitude obtained a β -coefficient value of .911 with the corresponding computed t-value of 28.660 and p-value of .000. It could be noted that the probability value is lower than the p-value of 0.05 that was set as the significance level in this study. Therefore, it could be inferred that the *consumer attitude* can best influence member behavioral intention.

This is in consonance with the findings of Akter & Islam (2020) that shows the consumer attitudes have a positive influence on purchase intent. There is also a positive relationship between

attitude and behavioral intention in purchases. In the study also of Billows and McNeill (2018), it was found out that attitude significantly predict behavioral intention.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of the Influence of Consumer Attitude on Behavioral Intention

Independent Variable	Behavioral Intention		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant	.409	3.086	.002
Consumer Attitude	.911	28.660	.000*
	<i>R</i>		.826
	<i>R</i> ²		.682
	F		821.423
	p		.000*

* $p < .05$ – Significant

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions are drawn in consideration of the overall results of the study. The customers have a positive attitude in choosing a specific gasoline stations in Samal District. Therefore, they consider their feeling and attitude as they buy products and services on a specific gasoline station and exert a favorable and good attitude. The behavioral intention of customers is oftentimes manifested in choosing a specific gasoline stations in Samal District. Therefore, they frequently have the readiness and willingness to perform a positive and good intention towards a gasoline station. The two variables were working almost dependently. The null hypothesis is rejected because there is a significant relationship between consumer attitude and behavioral intention in the choice of gasoline stations in Samal District. Thus, the behavioral intention highly depends upon the level of consumer attitude.

The foregoing findings and conclusions give way to these recommendations. Since the customers perceive that it is good to buy fuel at a specific gasoline station and if they will go to fill the fuel, they are willing to choose a specific gasoline station, so a gasoline station should improve their marketing strategy, like giving a discount or promo to their product, improve the quality of service and accommodation because customers oftentimes choose a specific gasoline station according to their

attitude and behavioral intention. Furthermore, future researchers may conduct the same study on

other fields or they can investigate other variables that will influence behavioral intention.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ajzen, I., 2008. Consumer attitudes and behavior. In C. P. Haugtvedt, P. M. Herr, & F. R. Cardes (Eds.), *Handbook of Consumer Psychology* (pp. 525-548). New York: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [2] Akter, S. and Islam, M.S., 2020. Factors influencing the attitude of women towards purchasing green products: An explorative case study of organic cosmetics in Sweden. *Journal of Consumer Sciences*.
- [3] Bhatt, A., 2014. Consumer attitude towards online shopping in selected regions of Gujarat. *Bhatt, A.(2014). Consumer Attitude Towards Online Shopping in Selected Regions of Gujarat. Journal of Marketing Management, 2(2), pp.29-56.*
- [4] Billows, G. and McNeill, L., 2018. Consumer attitude and behavioral intention toward collaborative consumption of shared services. *Sustainability, 10(12), p.4468.*
- [5] Blomqvist, A., Nyman, L. & Lennartsson, F., 2015. Consumer attitudes towards online grocery shopping: A research conducted on Swedish consumers.
- [6] Boru, T., 2018. CHAPTER FIVE RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY 5. 1. Introduction. *CHAPTER FIVE Res. Des. Methodol. 5.1. Introd.*, (December), p.41.
- [7] Chopin, M.C. and Darrat, A.F., 2000. Can consumer attitudes forecast the macroeconomy?. *The American Economist, 44(1), pp.34-42.*
- [8] Curtale, R., Liao, F. and Rebalski, E., 2022. Transitional behavioral intention to use autonomous electric car-sharing services: Evidence from four European countries. *Transportation Research Part C, 135, p.103516.*
- [8] Gupta, S. & Lehmann, D.R., 2003. Customers as assets. *Journal of Interactive marketing, 17(1), pp.9-24.*
- [9] Ho, S.F., 2013. A study on consumers' attitude towards online shopping on Penang famous fruits pickles-FASS Final Project (Psychology).
- [10] Jardeleza Jr, E.L., 2004. Customers' profile, buying practices, and satisfaction with services of a gasoline service station in Jaro, Iloilo City.
- [11] Kakunu, J.K., 2012. *Determinants of consumer preference in choice of petroleum service outlets in Nairobi* (Doctoral dissertation).
- [12] Khan, M., 2019. Consumer behavioral intention on purchasing Omera LPG.
- [13] Mothersbaugh, D.L., Hawkins, D.I., Kleiser, S.B., Mothersbaugh, L.L. and Watson, C.F., 2020. *Consumer behavior: Building marketing strategy*. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill Education.
- [14] Mwenda, S. and Oloko, D., 2017. Determinants of motorists choice of a petrol station in Kenya a survey of Thika Sub County.
- [15] Ndlazi, N., Zwane, T., Mgiba, F. and Chuchu, T., 2021. EXAMINING CONSUMER ATTITUDES AND INTENTIONS TOWARDS THE ADOPTION OF SELF-SERVICE FUEL STATIONS IN JOHANNESBURG, SOUTH AFRICA.
- [16] Pande, A.C. and Soodan, V., 2015. Role of consumer attitudes, beliefs and subjective norms as predictors of purchase behaviour: a study on personal care purchases. *The Business & Management Review, 5(4), p.284.*
- [17] Rashid, A. and Khan, N., 2017. Consumer attitude and behavior of religious consumers towards offensive advertisements. *Ann. of Behavioural Science, 3(2), pp.28-35.*

- [18] Sandhe, A., 2019. THE EFFECT OF CONSUMER ATTITUDE ON PURCHASING INTENTION FOR ORGANIC PRODUCTS. *International Journal of Research-Granthaalayah*, 7(2), pp.1-9.
- [20] SousaI, V.D., DriessnackII, M. and MendesIII, I.A.C., 2007. An overview of research designs relevant to nursing: Part 1: Quantitative research designs. *Rev. Latino-Am. Enfermagem*, 15(3).
- [21] Suki, N.M. and Suki, N.M., 2011. Exploring the relationship between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived enjoyment, attitude and subscribers' intention towards using 3G mobile services. *Journal of Information Technology Management*, 22(1), pp.1-7.
- [22] Tun, K.T., 2020. *Consumer attitude and behavioral intention in the choice of petrol station (A Case study in Dagon SeikkanTownship)* (Doctoral dissertation, MERAL Portal).
- [23] Tun, M.M., 2019. *THE EFFECT OF MARKETING MIX ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR TOWARDS IDEMITSU LUBRICANT IN YANGON* (Doctoral dissertation, MERAL Portal).
- [24] VERMEIR, I. and VERBEKE, W., 2006. SUSTAINABLE FOOD CONSUMPTION: EXPLORING THE CONSUMER "ATTITUDE-BEHAVIORAL INTENTION" GAP. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 19, pp.169-194.